

Институты контроля предпринимательской экосистемы на пищевых рынках стран АТР

Ольга Карпец¹, Екатерина Юрченко^{1,*}

¹Дальневосточный федеральный университет, Владивосток, Россия

Информация о статье

Поступила в редакцию:

17.02.2017

Принята

к опубликованию:

06.04.2017

УДК 336:5

JEL D 47, L 51

Ключевые слова:

безопасность продуктов питания, контроль качества, регулирующие институты, рынок продуктов питания, АТР.

Keywords:

food safety, food safety regulation, food quality control, food market, Asian-Pacific Region.

Аннотация

Качество и безопасность продуктов питания являются необходимым условием для обеспечения здоровья нации и роста производительности труда. Динамичное развитие стран АТР привело к росту спроса на качественные продукты питания. Несмотря на актуальность тематики, в проанализированных статьях из реферируемых зарубежных журналов не в полной мере описана предпринимательская среда на пищевом рынке с точки зрения относительной эффективности действующих институтов. В статье проводится сравнительный анализ формальных и неформальных институтов контроля на рынке продуктов питания Японии, КНР и Индии и оценка их эффективности. Предложены пути улучшения текущей институциональной ситуации в этих странах и обсуждаются потенциальные варианты применения опыта этих стран для российского рынка пищевых продуктов.

Entrepreneurial environment at food markets of selected Asian countries control institutions

Olga Karpets, Ekaterina Iurchenko

Abstract

The article addresses the issue crucial both for the economy as a whole and for every individual consumer since food is one of the basic needs for human beings. Quality of food influences health and productivity of every country's population.

However, market sometimes fails to provide correct incentives for the economic agents to supply high-quality products and in a number of countries the problem starts with the food deficit itself so that people do not start to think about its quality. If the government and its institutes are weak the labor force may show maximum productivity and economic development will be impaired.

The issue is even more challenging in Asian countries, due to the rapid growth of the Asia-Pacific Region, which results in higher demands for food quality. Although there is plenty of literature

on the topic, that demonstrate various approaches, relative efficiency of food safety control in terms of both formal and informal monitoring has not been examined in detail. The article intends to identify common and distinctive features among the instruments adopted by some countries (Japan, China and India) to provide their citizens guarantees that the food is safe for consumption. A method of comparative study was applied to assess the benefits and efficiency of each type of institution, which include government-provided (legislation) and alternative ones like consumer and producer initiated or third-party (mass-media). In conclusion, some possible suggestions to improve the current entrepreneurial environment at food markets of selected Asian countries control institutions are presented. Special recommendations were made for India due to its unfavorable situation at the moment. Finally, potential policy alternatives for Russia are presented.

Introduction and literature review

Safety of food regulation at a national level should be regarded as extremely important for a number of reasons:

- inherent market imperfections [1];
- in terms of international competitiveness of a company [2];
- for developing countries the issue of compliance stands up high in respect to their exports to developed countries [3];
- in concern of competition issues of co-regulation [4];
- shift of consumers preferences from the volume of food supplied to its quality [5];
- relationships between public and private food safety control systems [6];
- specific reason for Asia: dramatic change in diets [7].

Quality of food influences health and productivity of population therefore should be regarded as governmental issue. Asian-Pacific Region is characterized by rapid growth and while its population gets wealthier it becomes more demanding to food quality as well.

There are two types of institutions controlling food safety: public (presented by statutes and controlling and supporting bodies) and private or alternative, and they have to cooperate otherwise the second may strongly undermine the efficiency of the first.

According to H. Demsetz [8] “the existence of market failure does not mean that government regulations can necessarily improve upon the unregulated market, especially when one considers the positive role that market mechanisms such as liability and product quality reputation play in the provision of safe products, including foods”. Therefore efficient alternative institutions complementing formal ones are crucial for smooth operation of national food safety control system.

Despite the variety of approaches reviewed, it must be noted that the relative efficiency of food safety control in terms of both formal and informal monitoring has not been examined in detail.

Research methodology

The data on food safety regulation was gathered for three countries of Asia: Japan, known by high life expectancy; China and India as populous countries. We identified the major players in this sphere as government, consumers and producers and mass media and applied a method of direct comparative study to determine the most and least effective ones.

The main purpose was to identify those food safety institutions that influence country's population, food quality awareness, and overall monitoring of this market.

Analysis results

Institutions of food safety regulation existing in three countries: Japan, China and India are divided into two groups: formal and alternative institutions. The relative efficiency of formal institutions is compared in Table 1.

Table 1

Formal institutions of food safety regulation by country

Institution Form	Institutions by country		
	Japan	China	India
Legislation	Laws		
	- Food Sanitation Law; - The Food Safety Basic Law (2003) [9]; - Japanese Agricultural Standards law(2000) [10].	- The Regulations on the Administration of Food Hygiene (1965) [11]; - China’s Food Hygiene law (1995) [12]; - Additional regulations	- India’s Food Safety & Standards Act 2006 (FSSA).
	Areas covered		
	- food safety policy, risk assessment and management; - food quality standards and food related processes, parties and equipment; - Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare (MHLW)	- food quality standards, hygiene rules, monitoring, enforcement and punishment of violators; - does not specify how to deal with cases of mass food poisoning	- food quality standards, food inspections mechanism; - producing, storage, distribution and selling of food; - the system of governmental regulation of big food enterprise’s activity [13, 14]
	Authorities		
	- MHLW; - Food Safety Commission, local governments [15]; - Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points system (1995) [16]. - Japanese Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries (MAFF); - Food Safety Commission (2003) [17]	- Ministry of Health; - Ministry of Agriculture; - The General Administration of Quality Supervision, Inspection and Quarantine; - China Food and Drug Administration (2003)	- The Food Safety & Standards Authority of India (FSSAI); - The Bureau of Indian Standards; - Local authorities
	Responsibilities		
- risk assessment and management; - stability of food distribution channels; - food quality control system; - collecting information and applying new IT methods [18]	- food quality standards, hygiene rules, packaging and labelling of products, the mechanism of monitoring, enforcement and punishment of violators; - dealing with food poisoning outbreaks [19]	- food quality standards, hygiene rules, packaging and labelling of products, the mechanism of monitoring, enforcement and punishment of violators; - enforcement of FSSA [20]	

As alternative (informal) institutions may be complementary to formal ones we analyzed the major areas of their influence. By alternative institutions we mean the ones provided by market, and groups of economic agents involved in the establishment of such institutions for each country selected.

The areas influenced by alternative institutions provided by market are introduced in Table 2.

Table 2

Alternative institutions of food safety regulation, provided by the market by the country

Institution Form	Country		
	Japan	China	India
Consumers	Parties		
	- Consumers; - Consumers Associations	- Consumers; - China Consumers' Association (1984)	- Consumers
	Areas influenced		
	- food safety and food security problems; - expressing consumers' opinion and protecting their rights [21]; - food related education [22]	- food safety; - high quality food demand; - consumers' rights protection; - inspections of enterprises [23]	- slight influence on food quality problems due to low education level, low food quality awareness and poverty of consumers [24, 25]
Food enterprises	Parties		
	- food producers; - food processing enterprises; - food distributors, including supermarkets and store chains	- small and large food producers and retailers; - food processing enterprises; - other related parties	- food producers; - food distributors; - street vendors
	Areas influenced		
- food quality and hygiene with the aim to protect their good image	- food quality and hygiene [26]	- food quality; - food related equipment; - hygiene; - hygiene training for	

In addition to the agents analyzed in the table 2 third parties to the market (who are not either consumers or sellers) may also be important in terms of food safety control. For the three countries selected we determined two types of such players Mass Media and Science (individual scientists and institutions). Their relative efficiency is compared in Table 3.

Data presented in the table serves to prove the different state of development of informal institutions in the area of food safety. Japan wins by the scope of their activities and presumed results. For example, mass media in Japan and China went further than simple informing of consumers and Japanese scientists are involved into investigations of food novelties impact and consumers' informing of studies' results.

Table 3

Alternative institutions of food safety regulation, provided by third parties in different countries

Institution Form	Country		
	Japan	China	India
Mass Media	Parties		
	-all sorts of Mass Media; - Journalists	-all sorts of Mass Media; - Journalists	-all sorts of Mass Media
	Areas influenced		
	- informing consumers of food safety situation; - consumers' food quality education; - motivating of food enterprises	- informing consumers of food safety general situation and food poisoning cases; - investigating of food safety violations [30]	- informing consumers of food quality questions and raising food quality awareness [31]
Science	Parties		
	- Scientists; - Scientific institutions	- Scientists; - Scientific institutions	- Scientists; - Scientific institutions
	Role		
	- developing new technologies for food storage and transportation; - investigating of the impact of food novelties on the human health; - informing consumers of the results achieved	- researching food related problems; - developing new technologies	- researching food related problems; - developing new technologies [32]

Conclusions and discussion

The effectiveness of food quality control system in three countries investigated varies a lot.

Japan has the most effective system of food quality control. According to statistics of The Economist Intelligence Unit, Japan ranks 23 in the world and 4 Asian-Pacific region by product security level in 2016. Index of food safety in Japan is about 20,7 % higher than average [33].

In 1997 there was registered 1960 food poisoning out-breaks with 40000 victims [16]. In 2005 there was registered 1545 food poisoning out-breaks with 27000 victims, in 2012 there was 1100 food poisoning out-breaks with 26600 victims [34]. Big numbers of affected by food poisoning is the result of effective food poisoning monitoring system in Japan.

Chinese system of food quality control stands on second place. According to statistics of The Economist Intelligence Unit China ranks 42 in the world and seven Asian-Pacific region by product security level in 2016. Index of food safety in China is about 17 % higher than average [35]. However, the system of control for food exporting enterprises is much stricter than for inner operators. As the result, more than 99 % Chinese food export to Eurozone meet international requirements [36].

In 2000 there was registered 150 mass food poisoning out-breaks with 6237 victims, 146 of whom died. In 2005 there was registered 256 mass food poisoning out-breaks with 9021 victims, 235 of whom died [37]. In 2012 there was registered 173 mass food poisoning out-breaks with 6272 victims, 146 of whom died [38]. Reliability of Chinese statistics is questionable, as a majority of food-poisoning cases is not registered. The growing number of registered food poisoning outbreaks can be the sign of growing effectiveness of monitoring and rising food quality awareness of population. The food quality control system of China needs reforming in order to make it more streamlined. However, the effectiveness of the system is gradually improving thanks to measures undertaken by the government.

Food quality control in India is the least effective of the three. The number of inspectors is too small to enforce food legislation effectively. With economic development and migration of village population to cities, the popularity of street vendors selling food in cities is constantly growing. The research conducted by Sunita Mishra in 2007 states that about 82 % of respondents prefer to buy food from vendors then to go to the restaurant in evening [39]. The vast majority of vendors operates without license. Only 3 % of street vendors use gloves while cooking, and only 2 % of them wash their hands [40].

According to statistics of The Economist Intelligence Unit, India ranks 75 in the world and 17 Asian-Pacific region by product security level in 2016. Index of food safety in India is about 3.3 % higher than average [41].

Situation in the areas related to food safety is compared according to data on Global Food Security Index provided by Economist Intelligence Unit. This index includes a set of unique indicators, which measures (on the scale from 0 to 100 points) drivers for food security in 113 countries.

The usually discussed in literature benefits of food safety regulation include reductions in risks of morbidity and mortality associated with consuming foods that could be contaminated with microbial pathogens and other hazards [5].

Costs of food safety regulation are predominantly analyzed in terms of deadweight losses (DWL) and we have identified two approaches. Antle focuses on industry's cost of compliance, borne by both industry and the consumers of their products, as well as administrative costs borne by taxpayers and the deadweight loss associated with taxation [5]. Seitone and Sexton identify two sources of deadweight losses [42]:

- wastage of low-quality products since they cannot be sold – DWL borne by suppliers;
- excessive product transformation or quality enhancement – DWL borne by consumers.

Seitone and Sexton even suggest a model for computing the costs and benefits of food safety regulation but, firstly, it is constricted by efficient market conditions and secondly, acquiring such comprehensive set of data requires an additional research (including industry surveys) going beyond the limits of this article. Therefore we introduce a set of recommendations for Japan, India and China based on available official statistics and research literature analyzed [42].

There could be definitely seen correlation between population income level and effectiveness of food quality control system.

Japan as a developed country began to create and improve its food quality control system much earlier than China and India. The performance of formal institutions in this country is higher. Responsibilities of central and local governmental

bodies are clearly divided. Laws related to food safety are regularly reviewed and kept up-to-date. Corruption index provided by the Economist Intelligence Unit is the smallest among the three selected countries.

Table 4

Global Food Security by country [33, 35, 41]

Categories and indicators	Japan		China		India	
	Indicator score	% difference from average	Indicator score	% difference from average	Indicator score	% difference from average
Affordability						
Food consumption as a share of household expenditure	87.8	+25.7	64	+1.9	61.1	-1
Proportion of population under global poverty line	100	+27.5	70.7	-1.8	37.6	-34.9
Presence of food safety net programs	100	+32.5	100	+32.5	50	-17.5
Availability						
Sufficiency of supply	62.7	+2.5	76.2	+16	40.4	-19.9
Public expenditure on agricultural R&D	0	-13.4	0	-13.4	0	-13.4
Agricultural infrastructure	80.6	+24	80.6	+24	41.7	-14.9
Corruption	75	+38.5	25	-11.5	25	-11.5
Quality and safety						
Diet diversification	69.6	+13.3	50	-6.4	37.5	-18.9
Food safety	100	+20.7	96.2	+17	82.5	+3.3

Sources: [33, 35, 41].

Chinese rapid economic development boosted an increase of income level as well. Rising consumer awareness and demand for higher quality made food safety the issue of wide public concern. However, formal institutions of food quality control still need further improvement. Index of corruption is quite big. The main positive factor in this situation is government’s attention to the issue. There are implemented food safety net programs and government managed to allocate the required resources.

India has the biggest proportion of population below the global poverty line (or population living under \$3.10/day in purchasing power parity). The problem of food quality in this country has become an issue of concern only recently. System of formal food quality control institutions is not effective enough. The responsibilities of various governmental bodies are not clearly divided. There is a lack of financial and human resources for implementation of related laws and control of food market operation. There are corruption problems and the lack of food safety net programs.

It should be noted that in Japan and China formal and informal institutions actively participate in monitoring food quality, while in India informal institutions fail

to provide sufficient motives to improve food quality, and food safety may be supported just by formal institutions.

In perspective, all the countries reviewed should increase public expenditures on agricultural R&D. Introduction of modern technologies like IT-systems can improve food quality and facilitate control over the food market. In the long term, these measures can help to create a food tracking system that will provide consumer with data on each item purchased. However, usage of modern technologies and overall modernization of food quality control system could be expensive; therefore, countries should implement this measures with the regard for existing resources.

China and India definitely lack such an important institute as quality standardization system. Therefore the introduction of international systems of quality certification (ISO, HACCP and others) is highly recommended.

Both countries also need further improvement of population income level, which will lead to growth of demand for food quality. The operation of formal institutions in these countries should become more efficient in order to decrease corruption level.

In addition to raising income level it is important for India to supply sufficient amount of food to the market. Market saturation can raise consumers demand for quality, increase competition and provide correct incentives to producers to supply high quality products. Infrastructure development in agricultural areas will also result in higher food quality.

From the side of informal institutions an establishment of consumers associations can also be a useful measure. They may facilitate interaction between government, consumers and producers and help to protect consumers' interests. Educational level of population should be raised to increase food safety awareness and to improve the level of consumers' participation in food market monitoring.

The issue of food safety in Russia is as much important as in the analyzed countries because food in Russia is abundant and affordable (according to the Global Food Security Index) but its quality is lower than in Soviet period.

Russia has a rather developed system of formal institutions (different technical standards applicable to various types of food) but the enforcement problem with the formal institutions is quite evident and the institutions themselves are not efficient enough. Some big companies choose to pass voluntary quality certification (HACCP etc.) but the quality is still not guaranteed.

Corruption level aligns Russia with countries like China and India though Russia ranks higher (48 against 75 for India). Therefore the same recommendations in this respect are advised.

From the other side Russian consumers are not educated in food safety issues in order to be able to choose among certified and non-certified products. Consumer food safety awareness growth in Russia may enhance competition among food suppliers and raise the overall level of food safety in the country.

Список источников / References

1. Henson S., Traill B. The demand for food safety: Market imperfections and the role of government. *Food Policy*, 1993, vol. 18, no. 2, pp. 152–162. DOI: 10.1016/0306-9192(93)90023-5

2. Holleran E., Bredahl M. E., Zaibet L. Private incentives for adopting food safety and quality assurance. *Food Policy*, 1999, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 669–683. DOI: 10.1016/S0306-9192(99)00071-8
3. Henson S., Loader R. Barriers to Agricultural Exports from Developing Countries: The Role of Sanitary and Phytosanitary Requirements. *World Development*, 2001, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 85–102. DOI: 10.1016/S0305-750X(00)00085-1
4. Martinez M. G., Fearne A., Caswell J. A., Henson S. Co-regulation as a possible model for food safety governance: Opportunities for public–private partnerships. *Food Policy*, 2007, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 299–314. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodpol.-2006.07.005
5. Antle J. M. Benefits and costs of food safety regulation. *Food Policy*, 1999, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 605–623. DOI: 10.1016/S0306-9192(99)00068-8
6. Henson S., Caswell J. Food safety regulation: an overview of contemporary issues. *Food Policy*, 1999, vol. 24, no. 6, pp. 589–603. DOI: 10.1016/S03069192-(99)00072-X
7. Pingali P. Westernization of Asian diets and the transformation of food systems: Implications for research and policy. *Food Policy*, 2007, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 281–298. DOI: 10.1016/j.foodpol.2006.08.001
8. Demsetz H. Information and efficiency: another viewpoint. *The journal of law and economics*, 1969, vol. 12, №. 1, pp. 1–22. DOI:10.1086/466657
9. The Food Safety Basic Law: Law no. 48, *The Japanese Diet. 156th Session, May 23, 2003*. Available at: www.fsc.go.jp/sonota/fsb_law170418.pdf. (accessed 28.10.2016).
10. Nagamatsu M., Matsuki Y. Food safety and security system in agri-food chains in Japan. *Frontis – Wageningen International Nucleus for Strategic Expertise*, 2003, vol. 1, pp. 137–140. Available at: library.wur.nl/frontis/food_safety/-13yoichimatsuki.pdf. (accessed 28.10.2016).
11. Bian Y. The Challenges for Food Safety in China. *China Perspectives*, 2004, vol. 53, pp. 2–16. Available at: chinaperspectives.revues.org/819. (accessed 28.10.2016).
12. Tam W., Yang D. Food Safety and the Development of Regulatory Institutions in China. *Asian Perspective*, 2005, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 5–36.
13. Pal M., Hardikar A. Food Safety Focus on India: a Growing Market. *Hot source expert insights into safe, sustainable and high-quality food*, 2013, vol. 1, pp. 4–5.
14. Srinivasan G., Food Safety and Standards Authority of India. FSSAI, 2010. Available at: <https://ru.scribd.com/document/276834348/Dr-Srinivasan-FSSAI> (accessed 28.10.2016).
15. Onodera T., Kim C.K. BSE situation and establishment of Food Safety Commission in Japan. *Journal of Veterinary Science*, 2006, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1–11. DOI:10.4142/jvs.2006.7.1.1. Available at: www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3242078/ (accessed 28.10.2016).
16. Ushio M. Food Safety Regulatory Issues. FAO/WHO Global Forum of Food Safety Regulators. Marrakesh, Morocco, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. *World Health Organization*, 2002, pp. 84–89. Available at: <ftp://ftp.fao.org/docrep/fao/meeting/004/Y3680E/Y3680E00.pdf> (accessed 28.10.2016).
17. Nagata T. Food Safety in Japan. National Food Research Institute, 2007. Available at: http://www.groenecirkels.nl/upload_mm/7/9/2/a13d3ac5-2521-40d1-a3ae-e1-b587beefde_p14.pdf (accessed 28.10.2016).
18. Setboonsarng S., Sakai J., Vancura L. Food Safety and ICT Traceability Systems: Lessons from Japan for Developing Countries. ADBI Working Paper 139, Tokyo, Asian Development Bank Institute, 2009. Available at: <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/publication/155994/adbi-wp139.pdf> (accessed 28.10.2016).
19. Levitt T. China's top-down food safety system is failing. *Chinadialogue*, 2013. Available at: www.chinadialogue.net/article/show/single/en/6369-China-s-top-down-food-safety-system-is-failing. (accessed 28.10.2016).

20. Williams M., Banerji A. Insight: India's sour food safety record. Reuters, 2012. Available at: www.reuters.com/article/2012/02/13/us-india-foodsafety-id-USTRE81C06720120213 (accessed 28.10.2016).
21. Raymond A., Jussaume Jr., Shuji H., Yoshimitsu T. Food Safety in Modern Japan. *Japanstudien*, 2000, vol. 12, pp. 211–228. Available at: www.dijtokyo.-org/doc/dij-jb_12-jussaume.pdf. (accessed 28.10.2016).
22. Food Safety Awareness Rising in Japan: 2012 White Paper on Food Education. Japan for Sustainability, 2013. Available at: www.japanfs.org/en/news/archives/news_id034267.html. (accessed 28.10.2016).
23. Махров А.В. *О защите прав потребителей в Китае (правовой аспект)* [Mahrov A.V. *O zashhite prav potrebiteley v Kitae (pravovoyaspekt)* [Protection of consumers' rights (legal aspect)]. Available at: www.russchinatrade.ru/assets/files/ru-useful-info/O_zatshite_prav_potrebiteley.pdf (accessed 28.10.2016).
24. Sudershan R.V., Rao P., Polasa K. Food safety research in India: a review. *Asian Journal of Food and Agro-Industry*, 2009, vol. 2, no. 03, pp. 412–433.
25. GutbiSalim Mohammed S. Food Safety Knowledge among Women in Selected Areas in Khartoum City. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 2013, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 519–525.
26. 吴珊 百度搜索：“神器”还是“玩具”？[Wu S. Baidukuaisou: ‘shenqi’ haishi ‘wanqi’? [‘Smart chopsticks’ from Baidu: a useful gadget or a toy?]. Available at: tech.163.com/14/0910/16/A5PVFTQG000915BD.html. (accessed 28.10.2016).
27. Greenfield R. Demand Improved Food Safety Laws for India. Available at: <http://forcechange.com/69485/demand-improved-food-safety-laws-for-india/>. (accessed 28.10.2016).
28. Dixit S., Khanna S.K., Das M. All India survey for analyses of colors in sweets and savories: exposure risk in Indian population. *Journal of Food Science*, 2013, vol. 78(4), pp. 642–647. DOI: 10.1111/1750-3841.12068.
29. Sustaining food security from the streets Mass training of street food vendors on food safety and hygiene. 2013. Available at: nasvinet.org/newsite/sustaining-food-security-from-the-streets-mass-training-of-street-food-vendors-on-food-safety-and-hygiene/. (accessed 28.10.2016).
30. Cody S. Blowing the lid off food safety in China. Eastasiaforum, 2014. Available at: www.eastasiaforum.org/2014/08/28/blowing-the-lid-off-food-safety-in-china/. (accessed 28.10.2016).
31. Neetu C. Use social media to make pupils ditch junk food, Government tells schools. MailOnlineIndia, 2013. Available at: www.dailymail.co.uk/indiahome/indianews/article-2385578/Use-social-media-make-pupils-ditch-junk-food-Government-tells-schools.html. (accessed 28.10.2016).
32. National Health Policy 2002 (India). Enacted from 2002 by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. Available at: www.iapsmgc.org/userfiles/National_Health_policy_2002-2.pdf. (accessed 28.10.2016).
33. Global Food Security Index (Japan). The Economist Intelligence Unit. Available at: foodsecurityindex.eiu.com/Country/Details#Japan. (accessed 28.10.2016).
34. Food Poisoning Statistics. Ministry of Health Labour and Welfare, Pharmaceutical and Food Safety Bureau, 2009. Available at: www.mhlw.go.jp/english/topics/foodsafety/poisoning/dl/Food_Poisoning_Statistics_2009.pdf. (accessed 28.10.2016).
35. Global Food Security Index (China). The Economist Intelligence Unit. Available at: foodsecurityindex.eiu.com/Country/Details#China. (accessed 28.10.2016).
36. Контроль качества китайских продуктов питания [Kontrol' kachestva kitajskih produktov pitaniya [Chinese food quality control]. Available at: samit.su/delovoe-predlozhenie-iz-kitaya/produkty-pitaniya-iz-kitaya. (accessed 28.10.2016).
37. Shi H.G., Wang J.M. Major national food poisoning between 2000 and 2009. *Chinese Rural Health Service Administration*, 2011, vol. 31, no. 8, pp. 835–838.

38. 卫生部办公厅关于2012年全国食物中毒事件情况的通报 [Weishengbubangongtingguanyu 2012 nianquanguoshiwuzhongdushijianqingkuang de tongbao [Ministry of Health report on food poisoning situation in China in 2012]] Available at: www.moh.gov.cn/mohwsyjbg/s7860/201303/b70872682e614e4189d0631ae5527625.shtml. (accessed 28.10.2016).
39. Mishra S. Safety aspects of street foods: A case study of city of Varanasi. *Indian Journal of Preventive Social Medicine*, 2007, vol. 38, no. 1 & 2, pp. 32–35.
40. Thakur P. C., Mehra R., Narula C., Mahapatra S., Kalita T.J. Food Safety and Hygiene Practices among Street Food Vendors in Delhi, India. *International Journal of Current Research*, 2013, vol. 5, no. 11, pp. 3531–3534.
41. Global Food Security Index (India). The Economist Intelligence Unit. Available at: foodsecurityindex.eiu.com/Country/Details#India. (accessed 28.10.2016).
42. Saitone T.L., Sexton R.J. Impacts of minimum quality standards imposed through marketing orders or related producer organizations. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 2010, vol. 92, no. 1, pp. 164–180. DOI: 10.1093/ajae/aap005

Сведения об авторах / About authors

Карпец Ольга Викторовна, кандидат экономических наук, доцент кафедры менеджмента, Школа экономики и менеджмента, Дальневосточный федеральный университет. 690920 Россия, г. Владивосток, о-в Русский, кампус ДВФУ, корпус G. *E-mail: karpets.ov@dvfu.ru*

Olga V. Karpets, Candidate of Science (Economics), associate professor of the Department of Management, School of Economics and Management, Far Eastern Federal University. 690920 Russia, Vladivostok, Russky Island, FEFU campus, building G. *E-mail: karpets.ov@dvfu.ru*

Юрченко Екатерина Сергеевна, ассистент кафедры Тихоокеанской Азии, Восточный институт, Школа региональных и международных исследований, Дальневосточный федеральный университет. 690920 Россия, г. Владивосток, о-в Русский, кампус ДВФУ, корпус D. *E-mail: iurchenko.es@dvfu.ru*

Ekaterina S. Iurchenko, Assistant Professor, Department of Asian-Pacific studies, Far Eastern Federal University, Oriental Institute – School of Regional and International Studies. D Ajax Street, 690920, Vladivostok, Russia. *E-mail: iurchenko.es@dvfu.ru*